

Primal-dual methods for large-scale and distributed convex optimization and data analytics

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Abstract—The augmented Lagrangian method (ALM) is a classical optimization tool that solves a given “difficult” (constrained) problem via finding solutions of a sequence of “easier” (often unconstrained) sub-problems with respect to the original (primal) variable, wherein constraints satisfaction is controlled via the so-called dual variables. ALM is highly flexible with respect to how primal sub-problems can be solved, giving rise to a plethora of different primal-dual methods. The powerful ALM mechanism has recently proved to be very successful in various large scale and distributed applications. In addition, several significant advances have appeared, primarily on precise complexity results with respect to computational and communication costs in the presence of inexact updates and design and analysis of novel optimal methods for distributed consensus optimization. We provide a tutorial-style introduction to ALM and its variants for solving convex optimization problems in large scale and distributed settings. We describe control-theoretic tools for the algorithms’ analysis and design, survey recent results, and provide novel insights in the context of two emerging applications: federated learning and distributed energy trading.

Index Terms—Augmented Lagrangian; primal-dual methods; distributed optimization; consensus optimization; iteration complexity; federated learning; distributed energy trading.

I. INTRODUCTION

Primal-dual optimization methods have a long history, e.g., [1], [2], [3], [4]. Seminal works include, e.g., the Arrow-Hurwitz-Uzawa primal-dual dynamics [4], and the proposal of augmented Lagrangians and multiplier methods, e.g., [2], [3]; see also [5]. The augmented Lagrangian (multiplier) method (ALM) is a general-purpose iterative solver for *constrained* optimization problems. The underlying mechanism translates the task of solving the original “difficult” optimization problem with respect to the (primal) variable x into solving a sequence of “easier” problems (often unconstrained ones) with respect

to x , wherein the influence of the original “hard” constraints is controlled via the so-called dual variables. The ALM mechanism is beneficial in many scenarios; for example, it allows to naturally decompose an original large-scale problem into a set of smaller sub-problems that can then be solved in parallel. ALM can handle very generic problems, including non-smoothness of the objective function and generic problem constraints and has strong convergence guarantees, e.g., [1], [6], [7], [8], [9].

The past decade shows a strong renewed interest in primal-dual and (augmented) Lagrangian methods. This is because they are, by design, amenable to large-scale and distributed optimization. Indeed, very good performance has been achieved on various Big Data analytics models, including, e.g., sparse regression [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], large-scale model predictive control [15], and low rank tensor recovery [16], and also on various modern real-world applications, such as state estimation for the smart grid, e.g., [17], community detection in social networks, e.g., [18], image filtering, inpainting and demosaicing, e.g., [19], [20], [21], factorization problems in computer vision, e.g., [22], etc.

In this paper, we provide an overview of primal-dual methods for large-scale and distributed convex optimization. We provide a gentle introduction to the topic, followed by an overview of recent results, also suggesting novel insights and potential novel applications. In more detail, we focus on the following key aspects.

- **Approximate updates.** Several recent results consider the scenarios when primal and/or dual variables are updated in an inexact way. The works then study how the inexactness reflects convergence and convergence rate properties of the methods.
- **Distributed optimization.** Primal-dual methods have proved to be very successful in distributed consensus optimization, e.g., [23]. Therein, a set of nodes connected in a generic network collaborate to solve an optimization problem where the overall objective function is a sum of the components known only locally by individual nodes. In this setting, after an appropriate reformulation of the problem of interest, application of primal-dual methods leads to efficient and often to optimal methods. Furthermore, several existing methods that have been derived from different perspectives have been recently shown to admit primal-dual interpretations, which in turn opens up possibilities for further method improvements.
- **Complexity results.** While traditional studies of primal-dual and ALM focus on convergence rate guarantees with respect to the (outer) iteration count, more recent works

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focus on establishing complexity results with respect to more fine-grained measures of communication and computational costs, such as number of gradient evaluations, number of inner iterations, etc. These results give additional insights into the performance of the methods with respect to the actual communication and/or computational costs.

- **Control-theoretic analysis and interpretations.** It has been recently shown that primal-dual and ALM admit interpretations from the control theory perspective. This allows to interpret, analyze and design the methods with classical control-theoretic tools. This makes the methods accessible to a broader audience than before but also allows for improving the methods.
- **Applications.** We demonstrate how an instance of ALM-type methods, namely the parallel direction method of multipliers [24], can be applied to the emerging concept of federated learning. We capitalize on recent results on inexact ALM to show how some recently proposed energy trading methods can be modified to provably work, with (inner) iteration complexity certifications, under more general energy generation and energy transmission cost models.

We now contrast our paper with other tutorial and survey papers on primal-dual or decentralized methods, e.g., [25], [26], [27], [28], [29]. Reference [25] is concerned with ADMM, a specific primal-dual method, and it considers master-worker (star network) architectures, i.e., it is not concerned with fully distributed network architectures. In contrast, we overview here both the methods amenable to master-worker and to fully distributed topologies. Reference [26] provides an overview of distributed optimization methods, focusing on complexity, communication-computational tradeoffs, and network scaling. In doing so, the paper mainly treats *primal* distributed (sub)gradient methods. In contrast, we focus here on *primal-dual* methods for large scale and distributed convex optimization. Additional very recent works include [27], [28], [29]. Again, unlike the current paper, they mainly study *primal* distributed stochastic gradient methods.

In summary, our motivation for providing this overview is to present to a broader readership the following. 1) Primal-dual methods exhibit a high degree of flexibility, in terms of the underlying network topology to which they can be adapted (e.g., master-worker, fully distributed); 2) they exhibit a high degree of flexibility with respect to the ways (inexact) primal variable updates can be performed; 3) they are amenable to control-theoretic analysis and design; 4) several state of the art existing methods that were originally proposed from a different perspective (see, e.g., [30], [31], [32]) can be shown to be instances of primal-dual methods; and 5) primal-dual methods, appropriately designed, exhibit good, and often optimal, computation-communication complexity.

Paper outline. Section II provides preliminaries on ALM and related methods and presents how they can be applied in distributed optimization. In particular, Subsection II-A gives preliminaries on ALM. Then, we consider more traditional master-worker architectures (Subsection II-B), followed by a treatment of fully distributed architectures (Subsection II-C).

Section III provides control-theoretic analysis and insights into distributed ALM methods. Section IV provides a review of recent results on the topic. Section V considers two applications – one for master-worker architectures (federated learning, Subsection V-A), and one for fully distributed architectures (energy trading in microgrids, Subsection V-B). Finally, we conclude in Section VI.

II. PRIMAL-DUAL METHODS FOR DISTRIBUTED OPTIMIZATION

Subsection II-A briefly introduces ALM and some related methods; Subsection II-B shows how they can be applied on master-worker computing architectures; and Subsection II-C describes how they can be applied on fully distributed architectures.

A. Preliminaries

We now introduce the classical ALM. To illustrate, consider an optimization problem with linear constraints,

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{x \in \mathbb{R}^n}{\text{minimize}} && f(x) \\ & \text{subject to} && Ax = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $f: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the given objective function and A is a given matrix in $\mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$. Starting from an arbitrary point $(x^{(0)}, \lambda^{(0)}) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m$, the ALM generates a sequence of points $\{(x^{(k)}, \lambda^{(k)})\}_{k \geq 1}$ as

$$x^{(k+1)} = \arg \min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \mathcal{L}(x, \lambda^{(k)}) \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k)} + \rho Ax^{(k+1)}. \quad (3)$$

Here, $x^{(k)}$ and $\lambda^{(k)}$ are primal and dual variables, respectively. Further, the function $\mathcal{L}(x, \lambda)$, which is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}(x, \lambda) = f(x) + \lambda^\top Ax + \rho \|Ax\|^2 / 2 \quad (4)$$

and is called the augmented Lagrangian of problem (1), determines the functions being successively minimized without constraints in the ALM update (2). The constant ρ is a previously chosen positive number.

The convergence properties of the ALM have been studied in much detail, both for the convex and nonconvex settings; reference [33] is standard, while [34] lays out a more recent geometric framework, and [35] proves convergence under unusually weak constraint qualifications.

The convergence properties of the ALM are particularly appealing in the convex setting. Indeed, the landmark paper [36] links the ALM to the proximal point method for monotone operators,¹ showing that the ALM is just the proximal point method applied to the dual problem of (1),

$$\underset{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^m}{\text{maximize}} \quad \mathcal{D}(\lambda), \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{D} is the dual function $\mathcal{D}(\lambda) = \inf\{f(x) + \lambda^\top Ax : x \in \mathbb{R}^n\}$. This link transfers at once the strong convergence

¹The proximal point method for unconstrained minimization of a convex function $\phi: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ works as follows: $x^{(k+1)} = \arg \min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \{\phi(x) + \frac{1}{2\alpha} \|x - x^{(k)}\|^2\}$, where $x^{(k)}$ is the solution estimate at iteration k , and α is a positive parameter. The method converges at rate $1/k$ for convex functions; see, e.g., [37].

properties of the proximal point method to the ALM, a typical convergence result being that the sequence $\{\lambda^{(k)}\}_{k \geq 1}$ converges to a solution λ^* (assuming it exists) of the dual problem (5), while the sequence $\{x^{(k)}\}_{k \geq 1}$ converges to a solution x^* of the primal problem (1) (assuming, for example, that f is strongly convex).

An important feature of ALM is that the update in (2) can be done in an inexact fashion, giving the method a high degree of flexibility, but also giving rise to various method variants. Specifically, if instead of (2) we carry out a single gradient step on function \mathcal{L} with respect to variable x , we recover a method closely related to the Arrow-Hurwitz-Uzawa (AHU) dynamics (saddle point method) [4]:

$$x^{(k+1)} = x^{(k)} - \alpha \nabla_x \mathcal{L} \left(x^{(k)}, \lambda^{(k)} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\lambda^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k)} + \rho A x^{(k+1)}, \quad (7)$$

where constant $\alpha > 0$ is a primal step-size.² Similarly, when the optimization variable is partitioned into 2 blocks $x = ((x_1)^\top, (x_2)^\top)^\top$, and when the objective function and the constraint can be written in the following form: $f(x) = f_1(x_1) + f_2(x_2)$, $Ax = A_1 x_1 + A_2 x_2 = 0$, then updating x_1 and x_2 sequentially in a Gauss-Seidel fashion, followed by the dual update (3), gives rise to the celebrated alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM), e.g., [25]. See also, e.g., [38], [39], for analysis of inexact augmented Lagrangian methods.

B. Dual decomposition framework: Master-worker architectures

The conventional (dual) decomposition framework assumes a computational infrastructure with N computing nodes (workers), each of which can communicate with a master node. The relevant optimization problem then takes the form (1), with the objective function and the constraint given by: $f(x) = f_1(x_1) + f_2(x_2) + \dots + f_N(x_N)$; $Ax = A_1 x_1 + A_2 x_2 + \dots + A_N x_N = 0$. Here, we assume that the optimization variable $x = (x_1^\top, \dots, x_N^\top)^\top$ is partitioned into N blocks x_i 's, $i = 1, \dots, N$, where the i -th block is assigned to the i -th worker. Similarly, the objective function summand $f_i(x_i)$ is assigned to worker i . Matrix A is partitioned into blocks A_i 's, where all the A_i 's are available to the master and to all workers. We assume that worker i is responsible for updating the primal variable block x_i , while the master is responsible for updating the dual variable.

The augmented Lagrangian function \mathcal{L} can now be written as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(x, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i(x_i) + \lambda^\top \left(\sum_{i=1}^N A_i x_i \right) + \frac{\rho}{2} \left\| \sum_{i=1}^N A_i x_i \right\|^2, \quad (8)$$

and the ALM proceeds as in (2)–(3). Due to the quadratic term in (8), the update (2) cannot be executed in parallel, in the sense that each of the workers i updates x_i in parallel

²Note that (7) can be written as $\lambda^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k)} + \rho \nabla_\lambda \mathcal{L} \left(x^{(k+1)}, \lambda^{(k)} \right)$, i.e., (7) is a dual gradient ascent step. Clearly, the same applies to (3). In addition, it turns out that (3) corresponds to an ascent step according to the gradient of the dual function \mathcal{D} in (5).

with other workers. To overcome this issue, several algorithms that parallelize (2) have been proposed, including the diagonal quadratic approximation, e.g., [40], and more recently [41]. As presented in [24], an appealing attempt is to update the primal updates in a Jacobi fashion:

$$x_i^{(k+1)} = \arg \min_{x_i} \mathcal{L} \left(x_i, x_{j \neq i}^{(k)}, \lambda^{(k)} \right), \quad (9)$$

$$\lambda^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k)} + \rho A x^{(k+1)}. \quad (10)$$

That is, each worker i optimizes function \mathcal{L} with respect to x_i in parallel, while the values of the other workers' variables are fixed to their value before the current parallel update, i.e., x_j is fixed to $x_j^{(k)}$, $j \neq i$. However, it is known, e.g., [24], that the method in (9)–(10) may not converge. An interesting recent method, dubbed parallel direction method of multipliers (PDMM) [24], overcomes this problem and works as follows. At each iteration k , PDMM first randomly selects K out of N variable blocks, where the set of selected blocks is denoted by \mathbb{I}_k . Then, the following update is carried out:

$$x_i^{(k+1)} = \arg \min_{x_i} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(x_i, x_{j \neq i}^{(k)}, \hat{\lambda}^{(k)}) + \eta_i^{(k)} B_i(x_i, x_i^{(k)}) \right\}, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}_k, \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k)} + \Theta \rho A x^{(k+1)}, \quad (12)$$

$$\hat{\lambda}^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k+1)} - \Theta' \rho A x^{(k+1)}, \quad (13)$$

Here, $\Theta = \text{Diag}(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_N)$ is a diagonal matrix of positive weights τ_i ; $\Theta' = \text{Diag}(\nu_1, \dots, \nu_N)$, $\nu_i \in [0, 1]$; $\eta_i^{(k)} > 0$; and $B_i(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a Bregman divergence.³

PDMM differs from (9)–(10) in three main aspects. First, PDMM updates only a subset of primal variables x_i 's at each iteration. Second, the primal variable update involves a Bregman divergence, which makes the primal variable trajectory “smoother.” Thirdly, PDMM introduces a “backward” step (13) in the dual variable update to further smooth the primal-dual variable trajectory. We refer the reader to [24], equation (9), regarding the motivation for the backward step. Interestingly, when the constants $\eta_i^{(k)}$'s are sufficiently large, the backward step (13) is not needed, and variables $\lambda^{(k)}$ and $\hat{\lambda}^{(k)}$ coincide. We will further exploit PDMM in the context of federated learning in Section V-A.

C. Primal-dual methods for consensus optimization

We next consider distributed consensus optimization, e.g., [23], [42], [26], wherein a set of N agents collaborate to solve the following problem:⁴

$$\underset{x \in \mathbb{R}^n}{\text{minimize}} \quad f_1(x) + \dots + f_N(x), \quad (14)$$

Here, the convex function $f_i: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is known only at agent i . To achieve this goal, each agent can communicate

³Given a continuously differentiable convex function $\Psi: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the Bregman divergence $B: \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as: $B(u, v) = \Psi(u) - \Psi(v) - (\nabla \Psi(v))^\top (u - v)$. For example, for $\Psi(u) = \|u\|^2$, we get as Bregman divergence the Euclidean distance $B(u, v) = \|u - v\|^2$; for $\Psi(u) = \frac{1}{2} u^\top A u$, we get $B(u, v) = \frac{1}{2} (u - v)^\top A (u - v)$, where A is a positive definite matrix.

⁴For notational simplicity, we let the optimization variable in (14) be a scalar one; it can be easily extended to vector variables in \mathbb{R}^d , but the notation becomes more cumbersome, involving extensive use of Kronecker products; see, e.g., [30].

with a handful of other agents through an underlying sparse communication network, assumed undirected and connected. Note that this key object—the communication network—is absent from the formulation (14). A common ploy to bring it to view is to reformulate (14) as

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{x=(x_1, \dots, x_N) \in \mathbb{R}^N}{\text{minimize}} && f_1(x_1) + \dots + f_N(x_N) \\ & \text{subject to} && \rho L^{1/2} x = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where ρ is a positive parameter and L is the weighted graph Laplacian of the communication network (e.g., see [43], [44]), assumed to be connected. The constraint, which involves the matrix square-root of the semidefinite positive matrix L , ensures that all components of x are equal, that is, $x_1 = \dots = x_N$, thereby securing the equivalence between (14) and (15). Let $f: \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be defined as $f(x_1, \dots, x_N) = f_1(x_1) + \dots + f_N(x_N)$. The augmented Lagrangian and the ALM (2)–(3) to solve problem (14) are then, respectively, given by:

$$\mathcal{L}(x, \lambda) = f(x) + \rho \lambda^\top L^{1/2} x + \frac{\rho}{2} x^\top L x \quad (16)$$

$$x^{(k+1)} = \arg \min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} \mathcal{L}(x, \lambda^{(k)}) \quad (17)$$

$$\lambda^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k)} + \rho \nabla_\lambda \mathcal{L}(x^{(k+1)}, \lambda^{(k)}), \quad (18)$$

where ∇_λ denotes the partial derivative with respect to variable λ . The algorithm above further simplifies to the following:

$$x^{(k+1)} = \arg \min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} f(x) + x^\top \eta^{(k)} + \frac{\rho}{2} x^\top L x \quad (19)$$

$$\eta^{(k+1)} = \eta^{(k)} + \rho L x^{(k+1)}, \quad (20)$$

where the original variable $\lambda^{(k)}$ is swapped for the novel one $\eta^{(k)} = \rho L^{1/2} \lambda^{(k)}$ to pull off the problematic matrix $L^{1/2}$ from the formulation (as its sparsity does not mirror the sparsity of the communication network).⁵

In this formulation, agent i manages the i -th components of $x^{(k)}$ and $\eta^{(k)}$. Also, the update (20) is implementable in a fully distributed way, as matrix L respects the underlying graph sparsity. However, similarly to the dual decomposition framework scenario in Subsection II-A, the quadratic term $x^\top L x$ in the primal update (19) couples all the agents, spoils the otherwise nice separable structure of the primal update, and blocks a directed implementation of this method in a distributed setting.

This grim state of affairs, however, is easy to lift because the canonical ALM can withstand several changes without losing its main convergence properties. That is, the canonical ALM (19)–(20) can be used as a starting point to inspire more distributed-friendly algorithms.

In fact, there is a very high degree of flexibility of how one can perform the primal update (19) and the dual update (20); this gives rise to a plethora of different distributed methods for consensus optimization. We mention here a few examples while a more complete overview of the possibilities is provided in Subsection IV-B and Table I. For example, the ADAL

distributed method [45] changes problem (19) to one that separates across agents and adjusts the dual update (20) accordingly. In a different direction, reference [46] changes the exact minimization of (19) to an inexact one, showing that inexact solves of (19), when properly controlled, not only retain convergence but also are amenable to distributed computation (say, by tackling (19) with some iterations of the gradient method, each of which is directly distributed).

An even more aggressive change to (19) is to carry out but one gradient step from the current iterate, i.e., carrying out an AHU-type algorithm. This also gives an advantage of avoiding “double-looped” methods, where primal and dual updates are carried out at different time scales. The AHU-type algorithm blueprint leaves us near the structure of efficient distributed first-order primal-dual methods such as EXTRA [30], DIGing [47], and their subsequent generalization in [44]. More precisely, while EXTRA and DIGing have been developed from a perspective different than primal-dual, they are in fact instances of primal dual methods as first shown in [47].

To illustrate, we consider EXTRA proposed in [30], a method developed from the standpoint of correcting the fixed point equation of the standard distributed gradient method [23]:

$$\begin{aligned} x^{(1)} &= W x^{(0)} - \alpha \nabla f(x^{(0)}) \\ x^{(k+1)} &= 2W x^{(k)} - \alpha \nabla f(x^{(k)}) - W x^{(k-1)} \\ &\quad + \alpha \nabla f(x^{(k-1)}), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \end{aligned}$$

where $W = I - L$ is the weight matrix and $\alpha > 0$ is a step-size. The matrix W is doubly stochastic and respects the sparsity of the underlying graph. For the AL function in (16), it can be shown that EXTRA is equivalent to the following method, with $\alpha = 1/\rho$ [30]; see also [44]:

$$x^{(k+1)} = x^{(k)} - \alpha \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(x^{(k)}, \lambda^{(k)}) \quad (21)$$

$$\lambda^{(k+1)} = \lambda^{(k)} + \alpha \nabla_\lambda \mathcal{L}(x^{(k+1)}, \lambda^{(k)}). \quad (22)$$

On the other hand, the methods in [31], [47], see also [32], [48], utilize a gradient tracking principle and work as follows:

$$x^{(k+1)} = W x^{(k)} - \alpha s^{(k)} \quad (23)$$

$$s^{(k+1)} = W s^{(k)} + \nabla f(x^{(k+1)}) - \nabla f(x^{(k)}), \quad (24)$$

where $s^{(k)}$ is an auxiliary variable that tracks the global average of the f_i 's individual gradients along iterations. The method also accounts for a primal dual interpretation, as shown in [47], [32]; see also [44]. For example, following [44], update rule (23)–(24) can be rewritten as follows (here, $\alpha = 1/\rho$):

$$x^{(k+1)} = x^{(k)} - \alpha \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(x^{(k)}, \lambda^{(k)}) \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^{(k+1)} &= \lambda^{(k)} + \alpha \nabla_\lambda \mathcal{L}(x^{(k+1)}, \mu^{(k)}) \\ &\quad - \alpha W \nabla_\lambda \mathcal{L}(x^{(k)}, \mu^{(k)}). \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The primal-dual methodology allows not only to re-interpret many existing first order methods, but it also allows for derivation of some novel methods. For example, reference [44] proposes a method that introduces an additional tuning parameter matrix B that has the sparsity pattern reflecting the network. Reference [44] shows that specific choices of matrix B recover the EXTRA and DigING methods. The author

⁵Note that, in this way, the sparsity-incompatible matrix $L^{1/2}$ is only used to construct the problem reformulation in (15), while it does not play a role in the actual computations in (20).

derives a primal-dual error recursion for the proposed method, which allows to tune parameter B for an improved algorithm performance.

III. ANALYSIS AND INSIGHTS

We now highlight some of the ideas spawned by a recent thread, fertile and ongoing, of works that look at distributed optimization from a control-theoretic viewpoint. The control toolset enriches the analysis and design of optimization algorithms with many exciting insights and proof techniques, too many to cover in detail here; with the beginner in mind, we illustrate the use of the basic tool of the LaSalle invariance principle as a proof technique and the interpretation of the ALM as a basic proportional-integral controller.

A. The LaSalle invariance principle

The LaSalle invariance principle is a standard tool used in control to analyze the behavior of nonlinear dynamical systems. The LaSalle invariance principle is covered, e.g., in the book [49], which focuses on continuous-time systems; discrete-time systems are studied in greater depth in the recent tutorial [50]. Roughly speaking, LaSalle's principle characterizes the fate of trajectories of a given nonlinear dynamical system, say

$$\dot{x}(t) = \Phi(x(t)), \quad (27)$$

where $\Phi: \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ is assumed here, for simplicity, to guarantee trajectories for any initial condition $x(0)$ and for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$ (that is, no trajectory escapes in finite-time). Suppose $V: \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Lyapunov-like function for the given dynamical system, in the sense that V is smooth, has bounded sublevel sets ($\{V \leq c\} \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ is compact for any c), and does not increase along trajectories of the dynamical system ($\dot{V}(x(t)) \leq 0$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$, whenever $x: \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a solution of (27)). Then, the LaSalle invariance principle asserts that each trajectory converges to the largest invariant subset M of the set $E = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : \nabla V \cdot \Phi(x) = 0\}$ (usually, denoted $E = \{\dot{V} = 0\}$), a set A being called invariant if trajectories starting in A are fully contained in A .

As an illustration, we show how LaSalle's principle offers a quick proof of convergence for the distributed algorithm in [51]:

$$\dot{x}(t) = -\nabla f(x(t)) - L\eta(t) - Lx(t) \quad (28)$$

$$\dot{\eta}(t) = Lx(t). \quad (29)$$

Algorithm (28)-(29) can be interpreted as an AHU dynamics (6)-(7), or as a version of ALM (19)-(20) in which the primal update is changed to just a gradient step. The major distinction, however, is that algorithm (28)-(29) runs in continuous-time. Algorithms in continuous-time cannot be directly implemented in digital setups. Indeed, it is well known that the discrete time and continuous time algorithms are not equivalent, unless time scaling or stepsize choices are done properly or implicit discretization is used; see, e.g., [52], [53]. They are nevertheless worth investigating, if only, as a first step to probe the soundness of a given discrete-time algorithm, because proofs in continuous-time are often much easier and shorter, and can even trigger new insights (e.g., see [54]

for such a recent example). Continuous-time algorithms for distributed optimization feature, e.g., in [55], [56], [57], [58], [59].

Returning to the analysis of algorithm (28)-(29), whose purpose is to solve problem (15), we let $x^* \in \mathbb{R}^N$ be a solution of problem (15). We do not assume here such solution is unique but, for simplicity, we assume that the convex function f has a Lipschitz gradient with constant $C > 0$, that is, the inequality $\|\nabla f(x) - \nabla f(y)\| \leq C \|x - y\|$ holds for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$. This property further implies that the gradient is co-coercive, that is,

$$(x - y)^\top (\nabla f(x) - \nabla f(y)) \geq \frac{\|\nabla f(x) - \nabla f(y)\|^2}{C}, \quad (30)$$

for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Although a solution of (15) may not be unique, all such solutions share the same gradient: if x^* and y^* solve (15), then $\nabla f(x^*) = \nabla f(y^*)$. This follows from (30) and the Karush-Kuhn Tucker conditions for (15), which reveal that the gradient of a solution x^* is of the form $-\nabla f(x^*) - L\eta^*$, for some $\eta^* \in \mathbb{R}^N$ (and also, of course, $Lx^* = 0$).

Now, consider the function

$$V(x, \eta) = \frac{1}{2} \|x - x^*\|^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|\eta - \eta^*\|^2,$$

which can be readily seen to satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(x(t), \eta(t)) &= -(x(t) - x^*)^\top (\nabla f(x(t)) - \nabla f(x^*)) \\ &\quad - (x(t) - x^*)^\top L(x(t) - x^*) \end{aligned}$$

for trajectories $(x(t), \eta(t))$ of the dynamical system (28)-(29). From (30), we see that $\dot{V}(x(t), \eta(t)) \leq 0$ and the LaSalle invariance principle can be applied: it shows that each trajectory converges to the largest invariant set M of the set $E = \{\dot{V} = 0\}$, which, in this example, amounts to $E = \{(x, \eta) : \nabla f(x) = \nabla f(x^*), Lx = 0\}$; so, the point (x, η) is in the set E if and only if x solves (15).

The next step is to find the set M , which consists of the trajectories fully contained in E . Let $\{(x(t), \eta(t))\}_{t \in \mathbb{R}}$ be such a trajectory, that is, $\nabla f(x(t)) = \nabla f(x^*)$ and $Lx(t) = 0$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$. These equalities, when plugged in (28)-(29), imply that $\eta(t) = \eta$, for some $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and that $\dot{x}(t) = -\nabla f(x^*) - L\eta$, for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$. Finally, intersecting the last equality with $Lx(t) = 0$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$ gives $\nabla f(x^*) = -L\eta$. Therefore, $M = \{(x, \eta) : \nabla f(x) = -L\eta, Lx = 0\}$, which is the set of Karush-Kun-Tucker (KKT) points (see, e.g., [1]) for the problem

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize} && f_1(x_1) + \dots + f_N(x_N) && (31) \\ &x = (x_1, \dots, x_N) \in \mathbb{R}^N \\ &\text{subject to} && Lx = 0. \end{aligned}$$

To conclude, the LaSalle invariance principle says that the distributed algorithm (28)-(29) navigates any initial point $(x(0), \eta(0))$ to a set M in which each point is of the form (x, η) , with x being a solution of (15) (or, equivalently, (31)) and η being a solution of the dual problem of (31). This conclusion is partially contained in Theorem 3.2 of reference [51] (whose proof is omitted therein). Before moving to a new topic in the next section, we point out that other concepts of control, such as dissipativity theory, have also proved useful in establishing convergence of optimization algorithms, e.g.,

see [58], [59]. In addition, reference [60] gives a passivity-based perspective for a distributed optimization algorithm studied therein.

B. Proportional-integral controller

Interestingly, the primal-dual algorithm (28)-(29) can be interpreted as a widely used controller structure: the proportional-integral controller. Consider the typical control setup depicted in Figure 1, in which the controller system K acts on the plant G so as to make the plant output signal y track a given desired reference signal r .

Fig. 1: A typical control setup: the desired reference signal r is compared to the plant G output signal y to yield the error signal e ; the controller K monitors the error signal e and reacts by driving the plant with a suitable actuator signal u so as to cancel the error e .

A popular choice for the controller is the proportional-integral (PI) structure, in which the PI controller computes the actuator signal $u(t)$ as a linear combination of a term proportional to the error and a term that integrates the error: $u(t) = \kappa_P e(t) + \kappa_I \int_{-\infty}^t e(s) ds$, where the coefficients κ_P and κ_I balance the two terms and must be carefully tuned to ensure stability and other performance criteria of the closed-loop system.

Retracing the ideas presented in [55] and [56], we can cast the primal-dual algorithm (28)-(29) into the mold of Figure 1 as follows: consider a fictitious plant G with input $u(t)$ and output $y(t)$ that is determined by the state-space model

$$\dot{x}(t) = -\nabla f(x(t)) + u(t) \quad (32)$$

$$y(t) = Lx(t). \quad (33)$$

In a sense, this fictitious plant models the agents selfishly minimizing their private cost function—an accurate statement when the input $u(t)$ is off duty. The role of $u(t)$ is thus to nudge the agents away from their greedy trajectories so as to build a consensus, that is, so as to have $Lx(t) = 0$, which is the desired reference signal for the output $y(t)$. Thus, the error signal is $e(t) = -y(t)$. If we now adopt a proportional-integral type of controller $u(t) = e(t) + L \int_{-\infty}^t e(s) ds$ and plug it in the fictitious plant (32)-(33), we arrive at the primal-dual algorithm (28)-(29).

Interpreting an algorithm such as (28)-(29) as a certain kind of controller expands our understanding of the algorithm because many insights from control can be brought to bear, for example, insights about the qualitative behavior of the algorithm regarding classic control metrics such as overshoot or settling time. A good case in point is the work [61], in which known properties of several standard first-order methods such as the gradient method, the Nesterov accelerated gradient

method [62], and the heavy-ball method [63], find pleasant explanations through the angle of loop-shaping control synthesis. Furthermore, control-theoretic tools have been proved to be very useful in the analysis and design of primal-dual distributed methods. An excellent example is the small-gain theorem, e.g., [64], a standard tool for analyzing stability in the context of interconnected dynamical systems, utilized, e.g., in [47], [44], [32]. The tool has been proved to be well-suited, e.g., in analyzing the methods in time-varying networks settings, in which case it provides an elegant way to cope with the challenging time-varying dimension of the problem. As another example, [65] (see also [66]) provides a method for analysis of distributed optimization algorithms, where a small-sized semidefinite program (SDP), with the size independent of the network and optimization variable dimensions, is associated to the algorithm of interest. Then, the numerical solution of the SDP gives a tight upper bound on the algorithm convergence rate. Furthermore, the authors provide a novel algorithm dubbed SVL, designed based on the utilized control-theoretic approach, i.e., through optimization of the associated SDP. The recent work [67], which advances a canonical form for distributed first-order methods that not only encapsulates many known state-of-art algorithms but also explains, for example, why the early, slower single-state first-order variants could not do away with the diminishing stepsize.

As a final example, techniques from control also help in studying time-varying (convex) optimization problems, e.g., [68]. To illustrate, consider an optimization problem that depends on a parameter. This parameter thus sets implicitly the solution of the problem, and commands explicitly the iterations of any associated primal-dual algorithm. Imagine now that the parameter starts changing stochastically, as fast as the algorithm iterations are taking place. Such fast-changing solution cannot be tracked perfectly by the algorithm iterations, which raises the natural performance question: how good is this tracking, say, as measured by the mean-squared-error (MSE)? In control parlance, this question is about the L2 gain from an input signal (the time-varying parameter) to an output signal (the error between the iterations and the time-varying solution), with the underlying virtual system being the algorithm. Such an issue was tackled in [69], in the context of a primal-dual algorithm for wireless applications, by resorting to Lyapunov and LaSalle's standard techniques. As another example of this line of work, the more recent reference [59] uses arguments from passivity theory to study the L2 gain of a primal-dual algorithm from random disturbances to deviations around the problem solution.

IV. OVERVIEW OF RECENT RESULTS: INEXACT UPDATES, COMPLEXITY, AND TRADEOFFS

This Section surveys recent results on ALM and primal-dual optimization methods for master-worker and fully distributed architectures introduced in Section II. A major focus recently has been on designing and analyzing methods with inexact primal updates. While this is a traditional topic, a more recently effort has been put on how inexact updates translate into complexity of the overall algorithm, measured, e.g., in terms of the overall number of inner (primal) iterations to achieve

a prescribed accuracy. This kind of analysis more closely reflects the algorithm performance in terms of computational and communication costs with respect to traditional metrics in terms of the number of dual (outer) iterations. Subsection IV-A considers master-worker architectures, Subsection IV-B studies fully distributed architectures, while Subsection IV-C presents very recent results on lower complexity bounds for fully distributed architectures, i.e., consensus optimization.

A. Dual decomposition framework

The conventional (dual) decomposition framework for the augmented Lagrangian methods has received renewed interest in the past decade, e.g., [70], [15], and has been applied in various fields such as distributed control, e.g., [71], [15].

The recent results are mostly concerned with establishing complexity in terms of the primal solution sub-optimality and primal feasibility gaps. Therein, the focus is to explicitly account for and model the inexactness of the primal updates, which are for example carried out by a specified (inner) iterative method. Then, the goal is to establish complexity results in terms of the total number of inner and outer iterations for convergence. This translates into precise quantification of the communication-computational tradeoffs for solving different classes of problems.

Reference [15] considers a dual and fast dual gradient methods and assumes that the primal problems are solved up to a pre-specified accuracy e_{in} . The paper then establishes the complexity of the overall algorithm as a function of e_{in} and discusses optimal setting of e_{in} so that the overall complexity is minimized. Reference [38] considers a similar framework for *augmented* Lagrangian methods and establishes complexity of the overall inexact augmented Lagrangian methods. For an inexact accelerated dual gradient method, the reference establishes the complexity (in terms of outer iterations) of order $O(1/\sqrt{\epsilon})$, where the inner problems need to be solved up to accuracy $O(\epsilon\sqrt{\epsilon})$. An interesting approach utilizes smoothing of the dual function [72]; we refer to [70] for the method and the related complexity results. Reference [39] considers the augmented Lagrangian method when the primal updates are carried out via an inexact Nesterov gradient method (inner iterations). The paper then establishes complexity of the method in terms of the overall number of inner iterations, and it also proposes a method with improved complexity based on the addition of a strongly convex term to the original objective function.

The revival of AHU-type methods (see (6)–(7)) in the past one to two decades (see, e.g., [73], [74], [75], [76], [77], [78], [72]) is partly motivated by their success in imaging applications, e.g., [73], [74]. A canonical setting considered is on non-smooth convex-concave saddle point problems. Reference [73] considers a unified framework of AHU-type algorithms and shows that the methods converge at the optimal rate $O(1/k)$, where k is the iteration counter. Another line of work [77], [78] considers primal-dual methods based on the extragradient method [79] and demonstrates for methods therein also the rate of convergence $O(1/k)$. Reference [72] shows that the smoothing technique due to Nesterov also allows for optimal

rate $O(1/k)$. While the works [73], [77], [78] do not exhibit optimal rates in terms of other problem parameters like the function’s Lipschitz constants, the smoothing technique [72] coupled with the Nesterov gradient method exhibits optimal scaling with respect to problem parameters as well. Finally, reference [76] constructs a novel method that also matches the optimal rate with respect to the iteration counter and problem parameters.

B. Consensus optimization

We now provide an overview of primal-dual algorithms for distributed consensus optimization. A starting point for many of the algorithms is (17)–(18). We classify here the algorithms with respect to which variant of the primal-dual method they use as a “baseline”, i.e., we divide them into the classical ALM-based, ADMM-based, or AHU-based methods.

ALM-based methods. Several ALM-based methods have been proposed, e.g., [14], [46], [80], [81], [82], [83]. Reference [46] considers several deterministic and randomized variants to solve (19) inexactly in an iterative fashion, including gradient-like and Jacobi-like primal updates. Reference [80] considers gradient-like primal updates and proposes algorithms to reduce communication and computational costs with theoretical guarantees. It also shows by simulation that performing a few inner iterations (2-4, more precisely) usually improves performance over the single inner iteration round-methods like EXTRA [30].

Reference [82] considers an inexact ALM based on an augmented Lagrangian function with a proximal term added. The primal variable update is then replaced by a quadratic (second order) approximation of the cost function. Reference [82] shows that, provided that the dual step size is below a threshold value, the method exhibits a globally linear convergence rate.

Very recently, [81] proposes a primal-dual method based on augmented Lagrangian that employs a second order, quasi-Newton type update both on the primal and on the dual variables.

ADMM-based methods. An important class of primal-dual methods is based on ADMM, e.g., [84], [85], [86], [87], [88], [89], [65], [13]. Recent works approximate the objective function in the primal variable update via a linear (see [85], [86] and a subsequent work [88]) or a quadratic approximation [89]. In this way, one can trade-off the communication and computational costs of the algorithm. References [88], [89] show that, through such approximations, usually a significant computational cost reduction can be achieved at a minor-to-moderate additional communication cost. Recently, [90] proposes a censored version of the linearly approximated ADMM in [88] to further improve communication efficiency and establishes its linear convergence rate guarantees.

AHU-based methods. Several recent works have appeared which are based on AHU-type dynamics (6)–(7), e.g., [91], [92], [30], [32], [44], [65], [93]. References [94], [95] are among early works on AHU type methods for solving (14). The methods consider very generic costs and constraints and propose methods that build upon the classical AHU-type

Baseline method	Primal update	Dual update	Presence of double loop	Handling constraints
ALM: [14], [46], [80], [81], [82], [83]	[46]: multiple gradient or Jacobi steps on AL; [80]: multiple gradient steps on AL; [82]: quadratic approximation of AL; [81]: quasi-Newton approx. of AL; [83]: exact minimization of Lagrangian	[46], [80]: dual gradient ascent; [81]: quasi-Newton dual ascent; [83]: accelerated (Nesterov) dual gradient ascent on the Lagrangian	[14], [46], [80], [83]: double loop; [81], [82]: single loop	[14]: constrained problems; [46], [80], [81], [82], [83]: unconstrained problems
ADMM: [87], [88], [89], [65], [13]	[84], [87], [13]: minimize AL exactly; [85], [86], [88], [65]: minimize linear approx. of AL; [89]: minimize quadratic approximation of AL	dual gradient ascent	single loop	[13]: constrained problems; [88], [89], [65], [87]: unconstrained problems
AHU: [91], [92], [30], [32], [44], [65], [93]	single gradient step on AL	dual gradient ascent	single loop	[91], [92]: constrained problems; [30], [32], [44], [93], [65]: unconstrained problems

TABLE I: Overview of primal-dual methods for convex consensus optimization

dynamics (6)–(7). Reference [95] allows for public constraints (known by all agents), while reference [94] also allows for private constraints. The work [57] considers continuous time AHU dynamics and proposes a method variant that converges for balanced directed graphs. Reference [57] considers more generic convex-concave saddle point problems that, when applied to problem (14), translate into an AHU-type method. Reference [92] proposes a primal-dual method for more generic problems but which can be applied to (14), based on the perturbed primal-dual AHU dynamics [96]. For the case of general convex-concave saddle-point problems, they establish convergence of the running time-averages of the local estimates to a saddle point under periodic connectivity of the communication digraphs.

References [93], [97] develop exact variants of the popular diffusion methods, e.g., [98], [99]. A distinctive feature of these methods is that they relax the requirement that the underlying weight matrix be *doubly* stochastic, i.e., the matrix is allowed to be singly stochastic. The works [100], [101], [102] devise exact first order distributed methods for directed networks. The work [103] provides a very general framework of proximal exact methods which subsumes many existing primal-dual methods, including [48], [32], [31], [47], [88], [30], [93], [104].

Table I summarizes a number of primal-dual methods for consensus optimization, classified according to which baseline method they use (classical ALM, ADMM, or AHU). Table I describes what type of primal and dual updates the algorithms utilize, whether they are single or double looped, and whether they are proposed for unconstrained or constrained optimization problems.

C. Optimal methods and lower complexity bounds for consensus optimization

Very recently, lower complexity bounds for consensus optimization have been analyzed, and optimal algorithms that can

achieve these lower bounds have been proposed. These results determine what is the lowest possible (appropriately measured) communication and computational cost for any distributed algorithm and also give insights into the interplay between the two costs. Interestingly, in certain cases the optimal algorithms and matching complexity bounds are derived based upon or admit ALM or primal-dual interpretations.

The work [83] introduces a formal black-box oracle model that allows to precisely account for the complexity bounds. Therein, each node has a finite local memory, and it can evaluate the gradient and the Fenchel conjugates of its local cost function f_i . Further, each node i can, at time k , share a value with all or part of its neighbors. The class of admissible algorithms is then roughly restricted to the ones that generate the solution estimate as arbitrary linear combinations of the past gradients and Fenchel conjugates available in node i 's local memory. We refer to [83] for a more formal and detailed description of the oracle model.

We denote by \mathcal{G} the underlying communication graph. Next, quantity τ is the unit communication cost relative to a unit computational cost, i.e., τ is the time to communicate a value to a neighbor in the network, while the time to perform a unit computation equals one. They consider an arbitrary algorithm that conforms to the black box model above and utilizes the averaging matrix W that has the spectral gap γ .

Reference [83] shows that, for any $\gamma > 0$, there exists a weight matrix W of spectral gap γ , and μ -strongly convex, ℓ -smooth functions f_i 's such that, with $\kappa = \ell/\mu$, for any black-box procedure using W the time to reach a precision $\varepsilon > 0$ is lower bounded by $\Omega\left(\sqrt{\kappa}\left(1 + \frac{\tau}{\sqrt{\gamma}}\right)\ln\left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right)\right)$. Reference [83] further provides an optimal algorithm that matches the lower complexity bound above. The algorithm requires a priori knowledge of network parameters such as spectral gap γ and some knowledge on the eigenvalues of matrix W . It is also interesting to compare the achieved convergence time

with [104]. Reference [104] derives a convergence time for the algorithm therein of order $O(\max\{\kappa, 1/\gamma\}\ln(1/\varepsilon))$; the time exhibits a worse dependence on the condition number κ than in [83], but on the other hand it does not depend on the product of γ and κ , but on their maximum.

Reference [105] considers a similar black box oracle model but allows for lower ‘‘oracle power,’’ wherein the nodes’ ability to calculate Fenchel conjugates is replaced by the nodes’ ability to evaluate gradients of their local functions f_i ’s. The reference assumes that the functions f_i ’s are convex and have Lipschitz continuous gradients with Lipschitz constant ℓ . The authors show that, for any $\gamma > 0$, there exists a weight matrix W of spectral gap γ and smooth functions f_i ’s with ℓ -Lipschitz continuous gradients such that, for any black-box procedure based on the considered oracle using W , the time to reach a precision $\varepsilon > 0$ is lower bounded by $\Omega\left(\left(1 + \frac{\tau}{\sqrt{\gamma}}\right)\sqrt{\frac{\ell}{\varepsilon}}\right)$.

The work [106] establishes lower complexity bounds for non-smooth functions f_i ’s and a black box oracle model similar to [105].

We close the section by noting that, while some lower optimality bounds have been met, there is still room for improvements. Namely, the current methods that achieve the optimality bounds are often constructive and may be complicated, and may require an a priori knowledge of several global system parameters, which may not be available in practice.

V. APPLICATIONS

In this section, we present two applications of ALM and primal-dual methods. In Subsection V-A, we introduce for the first time ALM-type methods in the context of federated learning; more precisely, we describe how PDMM (11)–(13) can be used for federated learning. Subsection V-B considers distributed energy trading in microgrids, wherein we provide some novel insights.

A. Federated learning

Federated learning is an emerging paradigm where a potentially large number of (edge) nodes, or multiple clients (e.g., collaborative organizations), cooperatively learn a global model while performing only local update recommendations based on their local data. We refer here to the edge nodes or clients as devices. With federated learning, the devices keep their data locally, without the need for raw data communication, e.g., [107], [108], [109].

As pointed out in [108], the setting of federated learning poses several challenges to the design of learning and optimization algorithms; we highlight some of these challenges. First, due to the communication bottleneck, only a small subset of devices may be allowed to communicate with the server at a single round. Second, the devices may mutually significantly differ in their communication, computational, and storage capabilities. Third, the data available at different devices in general follows a different statistical distribution, where the distribution of the data is unknown both at the device and server levels.

More formally, the problem of interest is as follows. There are N devices and a single server, where each device can communicate with the server bidirectionally. The goal is to solve the following optimization problem:

$$\text{minimize}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} f(x) := \sum_{i=1}^N p_i F_i(x). \quad (34)$$

Here, $p_i > 0$, and $\sum_{i=1}^N p_i = 1$. We assume that p_i is known by device i and that all p_i ’s are known at the server. Furthermore, $F_i(x)$ is the empirical risk with respect to the data available at device i . The distributions that generate the different devices’ data can be different. Denote by $f_i(x) := p_i F_i(x)$. We also let

$$F(x) = F(x_1, \dots, x_N) = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i(x_i).$$

Recently proposed algorithms to solve (34) include, e.g., FedAvg [107], and FedProx [110].

We describe here how PDMM, [24], can be used to solve (34). First, we introduce the following (equivalent) reformulation of (34), analogous to the reformulation in [25] for consensus optimization. That is, we minimize $F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i(x_i)$, subject to the constraints $z = x_i$, $i = 1, \dots, N$.

The augmented Lagrangian function is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}(x, z; \lambda) = F(x) + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^\top (z - x_i) + \frac{\rho}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \|z - x_i\|^2.$$

We denote by $S_k \subset \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$ the variable blocks that the server selects to update via PDMM at iteration k . Here, we assign index i to variable block x_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, and index 0 to variable block z . The blocks in S_k can be selected uniformly at random from set $\{0, 1, \dots, N\}$, such that the cardinality of S_k equals M . We apply here the PDMM variant without the backward dual step, i.e., we assume that the weights that correspond to the Bregman divergence term in (11) are sufficiently large. We let the Bregman divergence term in (11) associated with the z -variable be $\frac{\eta_0}{2} \|z - z^{(k)}\|^2$, while the Bregman divergence terms associated with the x_i ’s are free to choose. Next, taking advantage of the fact that the z -update can be carried out in closed form, and simplifying further, one can arrive at the method presented in Algorithm 1. Variables z, x_1, \dots, x_N , can be, e.g., initialized to zero. We now comment on Algorithm 1. Interestingly, Algorithm 1 has some similarities with FedProx in [110], even though it is derived from a very different perspective, but it also has the following key differences. First, while in FedProx device i minimizes (approximately) function $F_i(x) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2$ (see [110]), with PDMM the latter function is replaced with⁶

$$f_i(x) + (\lambda_i^{(k)})^\top (x - z^{(k)}) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2.$$

⁶It can be shown [24] that the exact minimization of function $f_i(x) + (\lambda_i^{(k)})^\top (x - z^{(k)}) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2 + \eta_i^{(k)} B_i(x, z^{(k)})$ in Algorithm 2 corresponds to an inexact minimization of function $f_i(x) + (\lambda_i^{(k)})^\top (x - z^{(k)}) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2$. Hence we abstract the influence of the term $\eta_i^{(k)} B_i(x, z^{(k)})$.

Algorithm 1 A PDMM-based method for federated learning

Input: $K, T, x^{(0)}, N, p_i, i = 1, \dots, N$
for $k = 0, \dots, T - 1$ **do**
 (S1) Server selects a subset S_k of variable blocks
 (S2) Server sends $z^{(k)}$ to each device $i, i \in S_k$.
 (S3) Server sends the dual variable $\lambda_i^{(k)}$ to $i, i \in S_k$.
 (S4) If $0 \in S_k$, the server performs the following update:
 $z^{(k+1)} = \frac{1}{\rho N + \eta_0} \left(\rho \sum_{i=1}^N x_i^{(k)} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(k)} + \eta_0 z^{(k)} \right)$;
 (S5) Each chosen device $i \in S_k$ finds $x_i^{(k+1)}$ as a minimizer of: $f_i(x) + (\lambda_i^{(k)})^\top (x - z^{(k)}) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2 + \eta_i^{(k)} B_i(x, x_i^{(k)})$
 (S6) Each device $i \in S_k$ sends $x_i^{(k+1)}$ back to the server
 (S7) Each device $i \notin S_k$ sets locally $x_i^{(k+1)} = x_i^{(k)}$ (no communication required)
 (S8) Server updates all dual variables $\lambda_i, i = 1, \dots, N$, as follows: $\lambda_i^{(k+1)} = \lambda_i^{(k)} + \rho \left(x_i^{(k+1)} - z^{(k+1)} \right)$
end for

The difference in the inclusion of f_i with PDMM instead of F_i is minor⁷. However, the difference in accounting for the dual variable $\lambda_i^{(k)}$ is important. Intuitively, both the proximal term $\frac{\lambda}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2$ with FedProx and the term $\lambda_i^{(k)\top} (x - z^{(k)}) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2$ with PDMM serves to combat the drift that may appear due to the difference between the local function $F_i(\cdot)$ and the global function $\sum_{i=1}^N p_i F_i(\cdot)$. However, the effect may be strengthened with PDMM, due to the inclusion of the dual variable. Second, the two algorithms utilize different aggregation updates – see (S4) in Algorithm 1. That is, the aggregation step in FedProx takes into account only the x_i 's for $i \in S_k$, i.e., the x_i 's of active devices only. On the other hand, PDMM accounts for the latest historical value of x_i from each device i , even when at iteration k device i is not active. This may “smoothen” the update of z and implicitly incorporates history in the z -update rule.

When each of the functions F_i is convex, PDMM enjoys global convergence, and the expected optimality gap $\mathbb{E}[f(z^{(k)}) - f^*]$ converges to zero, where f^* is the optimal value of (34).

In the context of federated learning, it is also highly relevant to consider non-convex problems, e.g., for training neural networks. Interestingly, we can apply the results of [111] to obtain an algorithm similar to Algorithm 1 that works for non-convex F_i 's as well. More precisely, a direct application of Algorithm 2 in [111] leads to an algorithm very similar to Algorithm 1; the only differences with respect to Algorithm 1 are the following: set $\eta_i^{(k)} = 0$, for all i, k , $\eta_0 = 0$; in (S5) use $z^{(k+1)}$ instead of $z^{(k)}$; and (S8) is applied only to the λ_i 's for $i \in S_k$, otherwise they are kept unchanged in the current iteration. Applying the results in [111], the resulting algorithm converges to a stationary solution almost surely, provided that the F_i 's have Lipschitz continuous gradient, the penalty parameter ρ is large enough, and f is bounded from below. (See Theorem 2.4 in [111].)

⁷Actually, ignoring the term $(\lambda_i^{(k)})^\top (z^{(k)} - x)$, and allowing for different penalty parameters ρ_i across different nodes i , one can divide the function $f_i(x) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x - z^{(k)}\|^2$ by $p_i, p_i > 0$, to arrive at the function used by FedProx.

B. Microgrid peer-to-peer energy trading

We now present how augmented Lagrangian methods can be applied to distributed energy trading, e.g., [112].

Distributed energy trading has received significant attention recently, e.g., [112], [113], [114], [115], [116], [117], [118]. A major motivation for such studies comes from renewable energy generators. Many of these generators, called prosumers, can produce, consume, and trade energy with their neighboring (peer) prosumers within a trading graph, e.g., [118].

More formally, we consider N energy trading peers connected within an undirected graph $\mathcal{G} = (V, \mathcal{E})$, where V is the set of N peers and \mathcal{E} is the set of edges designating the trading capabilities of the peers.⁸ In other words, the presence of arc (i, j) means that peer j can buy energy from peer i . (We assume that the trading is symmetric, i.e., if $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$, then $(j, i) \in \mathcal{E}$ as well.) We denote by $\Omega_i = \{j : (j, i) \in \mathcal{E}\}$ the neighborhood of i , i.e., the set of peers that are allowed to sell energy to peer i .

At each time interval, peer i generates $E_i^{(g)}$ and consumes $E_i^{(c)}$ energy units. If $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$, then peer i can sell energy to peer j , in the amount of E_{ij} . We assume that the peers do not have energy storage capacity, and therefore each peer obeys the energy balance equation, as follows:

$$E_i^{(g)} + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} E_{ji} = E_i^{(c)} + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} E_{ij}. \quad (35)$$

Denote by $C_i(E)$ the cost incurred at peer i for generating E energy units, and by $\gamma_{ij}(E)$ the cost of trading and transferring the amount of energy E from peer i to peer j . Then, we can formulate an optimization problem of finding optimal energy trading transactions $E_{ij}, (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$, such that the total system costs of generation and trading are minimized:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize}_{E_{ij}: (i,j) \in \mathcal{E}} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N C_i \left(E_i^{(c)} + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} (E_{ij} - E_{ji}) \right) \\ & + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} \gamma_{ji}(E_{ji}) \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{subject to} \quad & E_{ij} \geq 0, (i, j) \in \mathcal{E} \\ & E_i^{(c)} + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} (E_{ij} - E_{ji}) \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, N. \end{aligned}$$

Reference [116] proposes a dual decomposition algorithm to solve (36), see Algorithm 2. The algorithm is derived based on a reformulation of (36) that introduces an additional variable ϵ_i and constraint per peer, $\epsilon_i = \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} E_{ij}$, and then dualizes these constraints, so that the resulting Lagrangian \mathcal{L} becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(E_{ij}, (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}; \lambda_i, i = 1, \dots, N) = \\ \sum_{i=1}^N C_i(E_i^{(c)}) + \epsilon_i - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} -E_{ji} + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} \gamma_{ji}(E_{ji}) \\ + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i \left(\epsilon_i - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} E_{ij} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

⁸More generally, \mathcal{G} can be directed, but for simplicity of presentation we keep \mathcal{G} undirected.

In Algorithm 2, $\mathcal{E}_i = \{\epsilon_i, E_{ji}, j \in \Omega_i : \epsilon_i \geq 0, E_{ji} \geq 0, j \in \Omega_i, E_i^{(c)} + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} (E_{ij} - E_{ji}) \geq 0\}$, and \mathcal{L}_i is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_i(\epsilon_i, E_{ji}, j \in \Omega_i; \lambda_j, j \in \Omega_i \cup \{i\}) = \\ C_i \left(E_i^{(c)} + \epsilon_i - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} E_{ji} \right) + \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} \gamma_{ji}(E_{ji}) \\ + \lambda_i \epsilon_i - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} \lambda_j E_{ji}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that Algorithm 2 is fully distributed, i.e., only peer-to-peer communication is utilized over iterations. In (S4) of Algorithm 3, α_k is the dual step-size. See also [116] for an interesting economics interpretation of Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Dual decomposition [116]

Peer i initializes $\lambda_i^{(0)}$.

(S1) Peer i sends $\lambda_i^{(k)}$, to its neighbors in Ω_i , and it receives $\lambda_j^{(k)}$, $j \in \Omega_i$.

(S2) Peer i computes $\epsilon_i^{(k)}$ and $E_{ji}^{(k)}$, $j \in \Omega_i$ by finding a minimizer of the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } \mathcal{L}_i(\epsilon_i, E_{ji}, j \in \Omega_i; \lambda^{(k)}) \quad (38) \\ \text{subject to } (\epsilon_i, E_{ji}, j \in \Omega_i) \in \mathcal{E}_i. \end{aligned}$$

(S3) Peer- i informs peers- j , $j \in \Omega_i$, about the energy it is willing to buy, namely $E_{ji}^{(k)}$, at the given price $\lambda_j^{(k)}$

(S4) with energy requests $E_{ij}^{(k)}$ from neighboring peers, peer i computes

$$\lambda_i^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \lambda_i^{(k)} + \alpha_k \left(\epsilon_i^{(k)} - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} E_{ij}^{(k)} \right). \quad (39)$$

$k \leftarrow k + 1$ and go to (S1).

While Algorithm 2 has an appealing structure, convergence guarantees it provides may be weak for certain models of energy generation costs $C_i(\cdot)$'s and energy transfer costs $\gamma_{ij}(\cdot)$'s, for instance when not all of them are strictly convex functions. Such scenarios are highly relevant; in fact, linear functions are frequently used, e.g., [113], [114]. In the context of distributed energy trading, we provide here novel insights how Algorithm 2 can be made amenable for more generic structures of $C_i(\cdot)$'s and $\gamma_{ij}(\cdot)$'s, applying the recent results on (inexact) ALM [38]. Namely, we construct the *augmented* Lagrangian function as:

$$\mathcal{L}_\rho(\{\epsilon_i\}, \{E_{ij}\}; \lambda) = \mathcal{L}(\{\epsilon_i\}, \{E_{ij}\}; \lambda) + \frac{\rho}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \epsilon_i - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} E_{ij} \right\|^2,$$

where \mathcal{L} is given in (37). We then propose to utilize an inexact ALM as in [38]. This modifies Algorithm 2 as follows. Step (S2) in Algorithm 2 (which was done by the peers in parallel) is replaced with the following step:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } \mathcal{L}_\rho(\{\epsilon\}, \{E_{ji}\}; \lambda^{(k)}) \quad (40) \\ \text{subject to } (\epsilon_i, E_{ji}, j \in \Omega_i) \in \mathcal{E}_i, i = 1, \dots, N. \end{aligned}$$

Problem (40) cannot be solved “in one shot” in a distributed fashion. However, it can be solved iteratively, e.g., through a

standard gradient descent, over inner iterations $r = 1, \dots, R$. It is easy to see that the inner iterations involve only peer-to-peer communications. Namely, every peer i sends current value of E_{ji} to peer j and receives the current value of E_{ij} from peer j , $j \in \Omega_i$. Utilizing the results of [38], we have that the overall (outer) problem is solved with accuracy ϵ_{out} in $O(1/\epsilon_{\text{out}})$ outer iterations k , where the inner problems (over iterations r) need to be solved up to accuracy $O(\epsilon_{\text{out}})$. Omitting details, we also point out that an improved complexity can be achieved when, instead of ordinary gradient descent, the Nesterov gradient descent is utilized. Also, it is possible to a priori determine the number of inner iterations R that guarantee that, at every outer iteration k , the inner problem is solved up to the desired accuracy $O(\epsilon_{\text{out}})$. It is worth noting that ALM has been considered before in the context of a related power systems problem [9]. However, this work is not concerned with the (inner) iteration complexity nor with a distributed, peer-to-peer structure, of the underlying computational system.

VI. CONCLUSION

The paper provided a study of recent results on augmented Lagrangian methods (ALM) and related primal-dual methods for large-scale and distributed optimization. We gave a gentle introduction to ALM and its variants and introduced control-theoretic tools for its analysis. The paper gave an overview of recent results on the topic, focusing on inexact updates, iteration complexity, and distributed consensus optimization. We capitalized on recent results in the field to draw novel insights in the context of two emerging applications: federated learning and smart grid.

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